

Attachment to the Study Report:

Coding of Childrens' drawings from Ovalau Island, Fiji, 2025

H1: Children will draw fishing activities that they do or observe or imagine	Fishing techniques are included in the drawing
	What fishing techniques?
	With a fishing boat?
	And if so, what kind of boat?
	Where?
	Who is fishing in the drawing?
	Do they themselves go fishing + information on their fishing practices
	Comment
H2: The drawings of boys and girls will be different, especially in terms of fishing practices, gears and grounds	Gender
	Do they go out fishing or not?
	Who taught them how to fish?
	Do they use bait, or what type of bait they use for fishing?
	Comment
H3: Children have good ecological knowledge, and this reflects that they are involved in fishing activities from a young age	Colours reflect different depths of the sea
	Presence or absence of turtles
	Presence or absence of sharks
	Presence or absence of whales
	Presence or absence of stingrays
	Presence or absence of dolphins
	Presence or absence of eels or snakes
	Presence or absence of finfish
	If presence, how many finfish in each drawing?
	If presence, size of finfish in each drawing?
	If presence, how many finfish names were mentioned in the interview?
	List of finfish names mentioned in the interview
	If presence, how many invertebrates in each drawing?
	List of invertebrate names mentioned in the interview
If present, how many kinds of invertebrates are in each drawing?	

	Presence or absence of corals
	Presence or absence of sea weed
	Presence or absence of sea grass
	Presence or absence of birds
	Other marine animals
	In the interview, children mentioned that they drew fish beds, fish houses, etc.
	Comment
H4: Some children will include a reef passage in their drawing (especially as there is one in front of their school)	Presence or absence of a reef passage
	If any, which reef passage(s)?
	In the individual talanoa, the child mentioned they have already fished in a passage
	In the group talanoa, the children mentioned they had already fished in a passage.
	In the individual interview or group talanoa, the children mentioned stories about a reef passage (passed on by their family)
H5: When asked to draw the reef, most children will draw ridge to reef connections	Sea
	Sand
	Island
	Flat Land
	Mountains
	Buildings
	Coconut trees
	Other trees
H6: In addition to fishing, children have other sea-related or reef-related activities	In the drawings, presence or absence of other sea-related or reef-related activities
	In the individual interview or group talanoa, children mentioned other sea-related or reef-related activities
	If so, which ones in specific